

1 **Phf activation connects DNA repair to Xist.**

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11 Citations

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1 **Results**

2 We studied the function of plant homeodomain epigenetic machinery Phf8 (Kdm7b) and Phf2 in molecular
3 regulation of the Xist non-coding RNA in somatic cells on the autosomes for homeostatic transcriptional
4 control of gene expression.

5 Figure 1: Knockdown of *Phf2* results in loss of *Zmiz1* and
6 *Zfp36l1* expression together with activation of *Dazap2*, *Baz2a* and *Dlx2*.

7 Figure 2: Activation of *Kdm6b*.

8 Figure 3: Activation of *Pax7*.

9 Figure 4: Loss of *Ago1*.

10 Figure 5: Induction of *Slx4ip*.

11 Figure 6: Loss of *Dlx6*.

12 Figure 7: Activation of *Phf1*.

13 Figure 8: Activation of *Tbx18* and loss of *Hoxd10*.

14 Figure 9: Activation of *Kdm7a*.

15 Figure 10: Activation of *Etv5*.

16 Figure 11: Activation of *Brd4* and loss of *Brd3*.

17 Figure 12: Changes in *Slx9* (*zdbf2*)

18 *Sox8*, *Sox13*, *Meis1* and *Foxo4* were also affected by *Phf2* depletion.

19 We also studied the function of *Phf12* in molecular regulation of the Xist non-coding RNA in somatic cells
20 on the autosomes for homeostatic transcriptional control of gene expression.

21 Figure 13: Depletion of *Phf12* in HEK293 embryonic cells.

22 Figure 14: Activation of *Hoxa9*.

23 Figure 15: Loss of *Dicer*.

24 Figure 16: Activation of *Snai2*.

25 Figure 17: Activation of *Dazap1*.